

Reaction to submergence of parents and F₁ and F₂ populations of crosses.

Cross	Submergence survival (%)			v ²	Ratio	Probability
	Parents	F ₁	F ₂			
BKNFR76106-13-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	84.3 0.0	72	54	0.21	9:7	0.50-0.70
BKNFR76106-16-0-1/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	80.5 0.0	19	51	1.12	9:7	0.25-0.30
IR8234-0T-9-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	73.4 0.0	65	41	9.45	7:9	0.01-0.001
IR21567-16-2-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	76.0 0.0	32	35	3.50	7:9	0.05-0.10
IR29012-4-1-3/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	81.3 0.0	72	43	0.02	7:9	0.70-0.90
IR31406-333-1 IR11288-B-B-69-1	10.0 0.0	72	59	0.31	9:7	0.50-0.70

Two types of segregation ratios were observed in the F₂: 9:7 for crosses where tolerant parents derived tolerant genes from FR13A and Kurkaruppan, and 7:9 for crosses where tolerant parents derived

tolerant genes from moderately tolerant KLG986 and Nam Sagui 19. These ratios can be explained by the complementary action of at least two genes. ■

Stress tolerance – adverse soils

Genetic variability in rice genotypes planted in sodic soil

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We evaluated the genetic variability and heritability of desirable traits in 56 rice

genotypes sown Jul 1989 in sodic soil (pH 8.9).

Planting was done in 5-m rows with three 35-d-old seedlings/hill at 25- × 25-cm spacing. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Maximum and minimum temperatures during crop duration were 32.7-27.4 and 26.4-14.9 °C.

All traits except flag leaf thickness showed a wide range of phenotypic

Range, mean, coefficients of variability, heritability, and genetic advance of 16 traits in 56 rice genotypes grown in sodic soils. Faizabad, India, 1989.

Trait	Range	Grand mean and SE	PCV	GCV	ECV	Heritability (%)	Genetic advance in % of mean	
Plant height (cm)	67.9-145.0	90.4 p	3.2	15.9	15.3	4.3	92.7	30.4
Tillers per plant	3.4- 8.7	6.0 p	0.6	21.3	17.4	12.3	67.1	29.4
Flag leaf thickness (mm)	0.6- 1.3	0.9 p	0.02	16.7	16.3	2.0	95.7	33.0
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	18.3- 56.5	34.0 p	1.5	23.1	22.5	5.5	94.4	45.0
Days to panicle emergence	77.7-122.3	101.0 p	1.6	8.8	8.6	2.0	94.9	17.2
Days to 50% flowering	82.0-131.0	104.8 p	1.2	8.3	8.2	1.4	97.2	16.6
Days to maturity	103.0-155.0	136.8 p	1.8	9.8	9.7	1.6	97.5	19.8
Panicles per plant	2.8- 6.8	4.9 p	0.6	24.1	19.3	14.3	64.3	31.8
Panicle length (cm)	18.4- 28.1	23.5 p	0.9	9.0	7.8	4.6	74.1	13.8
Spikelets per panicle	61.7-270.7	137.2 p	13.9	33.0	30.5	14.4	85.9	58.4
Filled grains per panicle	52.0-239.3	117.4 p	14.4	32.9	29.3	15.1	79.1	53.6
Grain sterility (%)	5.0- 41.0	14.0 p	2.7	55.4	50.3	23.2	82.5	94.7
Biological yield per plant (g)	12.7- 45.3	25.8 p	3.4	33.4	29.2	16.2	76.4	52.3
Grain yield per plant (g)	6.8- 21.6	11.4 p	1.6	27.6	24.0	13.6	41.3	26.6
Harvest index (%)	29.7- 62.0	45.9 p	4.8	20.9	16.4	12.9	61.8	43.0
100-grain wt (g)	1.6- 3.3	2.6 p	0.1	13.9	13.5	3.1	92.3	23.3

variation (see table). The phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) for all traits. PCV ranged from 8.3 for days to 50% flowering to 55.4 for grain sterility.

Tillers/plant, flag leaf area, paniced plant, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, grain sterility, biological yield/plant, grain yield/plant, and harvest index had high values for both GCV and PCV.

Tillers/plant, panicles/plant, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, grain sterility, biological yield/plant, grain yield/plant, and harvest index showed higher environmental coefficient of variability (ECV). This indicates that these traits were more susceptible to environmental and agro-ecotypic factors, especially to soil sodicity and temperature variations.

Grain sterility showed higher PCV, GCV, ECV, and genetic advance (in % of mean) than other traits, indicating this trait could be used in breeding for salt tolerance. Heritability was high for all traits except grain yield/plant.

Grain sterility, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, biological yield/plant, flag leaf area, and harvest index showed higher values for genetic advance.

Panicles/plant, flag leaf area, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, sterility, and yield may be good selection criteria for screening rice genotypes for sodic soil conditions. ■

Absorption of nutrients and their replaceable functions in rice varieties tolerant of and sensitive to K deficiency

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The experiment was conducted with two varieties: Xiang-Zao-Nuo 1 (XZN 1) is tolerant of K deficiency, Shuang-Gui 36 (SG36) is sensitive. Seedlings at the three-leaf stage were grown on complete and K-deficient nutrient solutions. Dry weight of seedlings was determined 34, 38, and 41 d after planting. Content of Cu, Mn, Zn, Fe, Mg, K, Na, and Ca in dried shoots was analyzed.

Seedling dry weight indicated that XZN 1 was not affected by K-deficient

growth medium (Table 1). SG36 showed marked growth reduction.

XZN 1 absorbed more Cu, Mn, Fe, K, Na, Mg, and Ca from the K-deficient growth medium (Table 2). SG36 increased absorption of only Zn, Mg, Na, and Ca. Fe and K absorption by XZN 1 was higher than that by SG36, but SG36 absorbed more Zn and Na.

It appears that in XZN 1, Fe, Mn, Mg, Na, and Ca substituted for K. These clear varietal differences in adaptability to low K availability indicates that breeding for K-deficient soils should be possible. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Table 1. Dry weight of seedlings grown in complete and K-deficient nutrient solutions

Days after sowing	Dry weight (mg/plant)			
	XZN 1		SG36	
	Complete	Deficient	Complete	Deficient
34	34.0	36.0	36.0	29.0
38	129.0	124.0	125.0	74.0
41	135.0	135.0	135.0	88.0

Table 2. Mineral content of 38-d-old shoots.

Element	Content (% dry weight)			
	XZN 1		SG36	
	Complete	Deficient	Complete	Deficient
Cu	2.0×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-3}	1.8×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-3}
Mn	9.5×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-2}	2.4×10^{-2}	1.1×10^{-2}
Zn	2.5×10^{-2}	3.1×10^{-2}	4.3×10^{-2}	4.7×10^{-2}
Fe ^a	3.8×10^{-2}	4.4×10^{-2}	4.3×10^{-2}	3.6×10^{-2}
Mg	0.40	0.65	0.58	0.77
K	3.09	1.49	2.93	0.63
Na	6.3×10^{-2}	0.24	0.12	0.76
Ca ^a	0.23	0.29	0.20	0.30

^aSampled 50 d after sowing.

Integrated germplasm improvement—general

CO 45, a new, medium-duration rice variety for Tamil Nadu

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TNAU80042 (IR17492-18-10-2-2-2) is a derivative of Rathu Heenati/IR3403-

267-1. It was named CO 45 and released in Jan 1990 for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu. It can be used as an alternate to IR20 and CO 43 in the second crop season (Sep-Oct).

CO 45 is 75-80 cm tall and matures in 140 d. Grain is long and slender with white rice.

It yielded an average 5.9 t/ha (10% more than CO 43) in breeding station trials 1980-81 to 1988-89. In multilocation trials 1985-86 to 1988-89, it yielded 4.1% higher than CO 43 and 14.9%

higher than IR20. In adaptive research trials in 10 districts 1987-88 to 1988-89, it yielded 10% higher than CO 43. In national trials 1985 and 1987, it yielded 17% more than Jaya and Pankaj (see table).

CO 45 is resistant to green leafhopper, stem borer, blast, bacterial blight, and tungro, and moderately resistant to sheath rot (panicle exertion is better than that of sheath rot-susceptible CO 43). ■

Chandan, a multiple-resistance variety released in Andhra Pradesh

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RNR74802, a semidwarf medium-duration culture derived from Sona/Manoharsali, was released in Sep 1989 as Chandan. It is recommended for general cultivation in Andhra Pradesh.

In yield trials in 1977-87, RNR74802 averaged 5.6 t/ha. That is 35% higher

Performance of CO 45 in Tamil Nadu, India, 1980-89.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)					Increase (%)			
	CO 45	CO 43	IR20	Jaya	Pankaj	CO 43	IR20	Jaya	Pankaj
Breeding station									
Coimbatore (1980-81 to 1988-89)	5.8	5.3	-	-	-	10	-	-	-
Multilocation trials (1985-86 to 1988-89)	4.8	4.6	4.2	-	-	4	15	-	-
Adaptive research trials (1987-88)	5.8	5.6	5.4	-	-	4	7	-	-
Adaptive research trials (1988-89)	6.2	5.4	5.2	-	-	15	19	-	-
National trials (AICRIP 1985)	5.0	-	-	4.3	-	-	-	17	-
National trials (AICRIP 1987)	5.3	-	-	-	4.5	-	-	-	18